

Paper 37

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS E-BANKING SERVICES, A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS IN UJIRE***Vignesh Pai B. H., **Padmini Y. S., ***Vijetha Pai B. H.***2nd M.COM, SDM College (Autonomous) UjireEmail: bhvigneshpai@gmail.com**2nd M.COM, SDM College (Autonomous) UjireEmail: Raniprishabharadhwaj@gmail.com***2nd M.SC, SDM College (Autonomous), UjireEmail: Vijetha.paibh@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Bank industry is most favoured industry for the development of the country. From the past few years banks have taken revolutionary steps to satisfy its valuable customers. The technology has strengthened the banking sector, the services provided by them have been updated and also uplifted the citizens of the world. The time has emerged for each and every bank to go electronically. This paper studies the role of e-banking towards the customers. The paper has made an attempt to investigate the satisfaction level of customers towards e-banking services provided by various public sector banks in Ujire. The study utilises the research paper and structured questionnaire is developed and distributed to collect the primary responses based on convenience sampling method. Results and findings are generalised through table and graph.

Keywords: Bank, Services, Technology, e-banking, customers.

1. Introduction

E-banking or electronic banking is a major innovation in the field of banking earlier banking was conducted in a very traditional manner there were no such innovation Electronic banking makes banking convenient on your schedule. Many people are now able to avoid the rush to get to the bank before it closes, as they can bank from a home computer or via automatic teller machine (ATM). Although the two systems are different, ATMs and online banking are the two types of electronic banking systems in use today. Electronic banking (E-banking) is a generic term encompassing internet banking, telephone banking, mobile banking etc. e-banking is a process of delivery of banking services and products through electronic channels such as telephone, internet, cell phone etc. Several initiatives taken by the RBI have facilitated the development of E-banking in India. The RBI has made considerable progress in consolidating the existing payment and settlement systems, and in upgrading technology with a view to establishing an efficient, integrated and secure system functioning in a real-time environment, which further helped the development of E-banking in India. E-banking has experienced strong and sustained growth. With rigid controls giving way to deregulation, banks are gearing up their communications infrastructure to obtain a competitive edge from E-banking. Thus it is fast becoming a reality in India. E-banking is fast becoming a strategic necessity for most commercial banks, as competition

increases from private banks. Though de-regulation may have had an impact on the banking industry in general. There is a better price discovery process as more and more markets gain integrated real-time and improved access to these trading and data-dissemination platforms. At the same time, however, many changes are still required in technology, access infrastructure and banking regulation. Virtually all banks use banking software at their head. A quarter of local banks, provide Credit card and point of sale services major cities, ATM and internet banking are expanding rapidly. However, E-Banking is the product of different generations of electronic transactions. Since its inception, electronic banking or online banking has gone through different transitions. Automated teller machines (ATMs) were the first well-known machines to provide electronic access to customers.

2. Literature review

1. Mr. Lakshmi Narayana.K, Mr. Sri Hari.V, Dr.P. Paramashivaiah (April 2013)

The study focused on investigating the major factors that influence online customers' satisfaction with the overall service quality of their banks. The study going to help the bank management not only in improving the level of satisfaction but also strengthening the bond between the banks and their customers. The results have also shown that pricing and bank charges related factors, namely Interest Policy and Bank Charging, are not significant. The researcher believes that customers' identification with the considered factors do not have a significant influence on their overall satisfaction. This research study revealed that Banking Needs, followed by Core Services, Problem Resolution, Cost Saved, Convenience and Risk and Privacy Concerns were the major factors that strongly affect the overall satisfaction of online consumers.

2. Md. Abdul Bashir, Mass Hareeza Ali, Md.Reaz (December 2015)

The study made an attempt to analyse the Customer's Satisfaction towards E-banking in Bangladesh. The research work made an attempt to find out the status of e-banking by customer satisfaction and importance level on different dimension of e-products like ATM, Credit Card, Internet/Online, Tele banking, and SMS Banking. The study revealed that Technological development is essential for making e-banking product and services familiar to customers. Banks should give concentration to its promotional activities to attract customers to involve e-banking services rather than conventional branch-based banking. The study also says that All Banks in Bangladesh should require ATM booths all over the country and should start to deposit money by ATM.

3. Reeta. Manju Asht (January 2016)

The study endeavors to explore the online customer services provided by the banking industry in India and additionally discussed the magnification rate and future prospects of the e-banking services provided by the Indian banks . The study found that there is lack of preparedness on the part of both Banks and customers in the adoption of incipient technological changes. There is lack of congruous infrastructure for the installation of e-delivery channels. Indian banks are making sincere efforts for the adoption of advanced technology and for installation of e-delivery channels, but it should be still improved. The study also states that Government should magnify investments for the construction of well-furnished building and infrastructure.

4. Shilpa Vyas

The study made an attempt to study the Impact of E-Banking on Traditional Banking Services. The study found that E-banking transactions are much cheaper than branch or even phone transactions. The start-up costs of an e-bank are high. Establishing a trusted

brand is very costly as it requires significant advertising expenditure in addition to the purchase of expensive technology.

5. Dr. M. Vasani (December 2017)

The research was focussed on customers satisfaction towards Internet banking of ICICI bank in erode city. The study has been conducted in order to meticulously evaluate and examine the level of satisfaction towards internet banking services. The study also had the objective to observe and analyse the purpose of using internet banking. The study revealed that the banker should configure security systems and firewalls to the highest security consistent with the level of protection according to customer requirements. The banker should reduce the cumbersome formalities for getting internet banking facility and should reduce the processing charges for NEFT and RTGS. The study suggests that banks should arrange demonstration programs for the customers, so that customers can understand the process of e-banking properly and can enjoy all the services provided by bank.

3. Objective

- To know customers satisfaction level towards e-banking service.
- To understand the concept of e-banking in rural area.
- To study customers awareness and satisfaction level about e-banking in ujire

4. Research methodology

The study is based mainly on primary data and supported by the secondary data. The primary data is collected from the customers with the help of questionnaire to evaluate the customer's prospective. For this purpose a structured questionnaire is prepared for the research. Secondary data are obtained from the existing research articles on the research topic. Data gathered through secondary used to formulate conceptual framework for the study and used as source for the development of primary data collection instruments.

Primary data: Self report questionnaire.

Sample size: 100

Sampling method: convenient sampling method

Analysis: data collected through questionnaire present in table and graph for the future analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table no 1: Gender

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	54	54
Female	46	46
Total	100	100

Figure no 1

Source: Primary Data

The above chart reveals that out 100 respondents 54% of the respondents are male and 46% of the respondents are female.

Table no 2: Respondents awareness towards e-banking

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Highly aware	62	62
Aware	22	22
Neutral	8	8
Unaware	8	8
Highly unaware	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 2

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that out of 100 respondents 62% respondents highly aware towards e-banking ,22% of the respondents aware of e-banking ,8% of the respondents are neutral and remaining 8% of the respondents unaware towards e-banking service.

Table no 3: Internet banking service is less costly than other banking services

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	54	54
Agree	16	16
Neither agree nor Disagree	22	22
Disagree	4	4
Strongly disagree	4	4
Total	100	100

Figure no 3

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 54% of the respondents strongly agree that internet banking service is less costly compare to other banking service, 16% of the respondents agree that internet banking service is less costly when compared toto other banking service. 22% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, ,4% of the respondents disagree above statement and remaining 4% strongly disagrees because of lack of awareness about e-banking service.

Table no 4: Internet banking transaction procedures are simple and straightforward.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	36	36
Agree	26	26
Neither agree nor Disagree	22	22
Disagree	12	12
Strongly disagree	6	6
Total	100	100

Figure no 4:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart depicts that 34% of the respondents strongly agree internet banking is simple and straight forward process, 26% of the respondents agree above statement, 22% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree the internet banking process simple and straight forward, 12% of the respondents disagrees above statement and remaining 6% of the respondents strongly disagree that internet banking transaction procedure are simple and straight forward.

Table no 5: Using the e-banking is an easy task

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	30	30
Agree	32	32
Neither agree nor Disagree	28	28
Disagree	8	8
Strongly disagree	2	2
Total	100	100

Figure no 5:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 32% of the respondents agree the e-banking using is an easy, 30% Of the respondents strongly agree the using of e-banking is an easy task, 28% of the respondents neither agree nor disagrees the above statement ,8% of the respondents disagree e-banking using and remaining 2% strongly disagree that using of an e-banking is not easy.

Table no 6: Respondents satisfaction level with e-banking because they do not have to go to bank.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	27	27
Agree	31	31
Neither agree nor Disagree	25	25
Disagree	13	13
Strongly disagree	4	4
Total	100	100

Figure no 6:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 31% of the respondents agree the satisfaction level of e-banking, 27% of the respondents strongly agree the satisfaction level of e-banking, 25% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 13% of the respondents disagree above statement and remaining 4% of the respondents strongly disagree above statement.

Table no 7: Banks are providing timely information about e-banking to the customers.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	28	28
Agree	18	18
Neither agree nor Disagree	24	24
Disagree	18	18
Strongly disagree	12	12
Total	100	100

Figure no 7:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 28% of the respondents strongly agree that banks are providing timely information about e-banking to customers. 18% of the respondents agree the banks are providing timely information 24% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with the above statement, 18% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 12% of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement saying banks are not providing timely information to customers.

Table no 8: Respondents knowledge about the e-banking transactions

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	21	21
Agree	27	27
Neither agree nor Disagree	33	33
Disagree	16	16
Strongly disagree	3	3
Total	100	100

Figure no 8:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 21% of the respondents strongly agree that they have proper knowledge about e-banking. 27% of the respondents agree the proper knowledge about e-banking transaction, 33% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 16% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 3% of the respondents strongly disagree that they do not have proper knowledge about e-banking transactions.

Table no 9: Personal data of customers under e-banking is protected

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	17	17
Agree	21	21
Neither agree nor Disagree	32	32
Disagree	16	16
Strongly disagree	14	14
Total	100	100

Figure no 9:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 17% of the respondents strongly agree that Personal data of customers under e-banking is protected by bank authority, 21% of the respondents agree with the statement, 32% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 16% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 14% of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement saying that bank authority do not protect customers personal information.

Table no 10: Internet banking is more effective than branch banking about time saving.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	34	34
Agree	31	31
Neither agree nor Disagree	21	21
Disagree	9	9
Strongly disagree	5	5
Total	100	100

Figure no 10:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 34% of the respondents strongly agree internet banking more effective than branch banking, 31% of the respondents agrees the internet bank saving time. 21% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 9% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 5% of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement saying that internet banking is not much effective than branch banking.

Table no 11: Websites which offer e-banking services are safe

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	16	16
Agree	20	20
Neither agree nor Disagree	29	29
Disagree	19	19
Strongly disagree	16	16
Total	100	100

Figure no 11:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 16% of the respondents strongly agree websites which offer e-banking services are safer, 20% of the respondents agree that websites offer e-banking service are safe, 29% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with above statement, 19% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 16% of the respondents strongly disagree with the above statement saying websites which offer e-banking services are not safer.

Table no 12: e-banking is convenient because it eliminates the risk of carrying cash.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	41	41
Agree	36	36
Neither agree nor Disagree	18	18
Disagree	5	5
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 12:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 41% of the respondents strongly agree that e-banking service is convenient, 36% of the respondents agree the above statement saying e-banking service is convenient, 18% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 5% of the respondents disagree with the above statement. None of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement.

Table no 13: If respondents face any problem about e-banking service, Banks authorities solve it

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	21	21
Agree	25	25
Neither agree nor Disagree	24	24
Disagree	18	18
Strongly disagree	12	12
Total	100	100

Figure no 13:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 21% of the respondents strongly agree that if respondents face any problem from e-banking bank authorities solve it in a right way, 25% of the respondents agree the above statement, 24% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree the above statement, 18% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 12% of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement saying banking authorities do not solve e-banking problem faced by customers.

Table no 14: Respondents suggest others to use e-banking services

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	31	31
Agree	37	37
Neither agree nor Disagree	27	27
Disagree	5	5
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 14:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 31% of the respondents strongly agree, 37% of the respondents agree the above statement saying that they suggest others to use e-banking services. 36% of the respondents agrees the above statement, 27% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with the statement, 5% of the respondents disagree that they do not suggest others to use e-banking service. None of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement.

Table no 15: Respondents Willingness to continue e-banking

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	33	33
Agree	35	35
Neither agree nor Disagree	21	21
Disagree	11	11
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 15:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 33% of the respondents strongly agree, 35% of the respondents agrees the above statement saying they are willing to continue e-banking service offered by bank. 21% respondents neither agree nor disagree with the above statement ,11% of respondents disagreed that they not willing to continue e-banking service offered by the bank. None of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement.

Table no 16: Respondents overall rating towards e-banking service

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
5	24	24
4	32	32
3	22	22
2	14	14
1	8	8
Total	100	100

Figure no 16:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 24% of the respondents rated as 5 for the e-banking service, 32% of the respondents given the rating as 4 out of 5 saying e-banking services has satisfied them, 22% of the respondents rated 3, 14% of the respondents rated as 2 and remaining 8% of the respondents rated as 1 out of 5 saying e-banking services has to be improved to reach all customers.

Findings

- Majority (84%) of the respondents are aware about e-banking service.
- Majority (70%) of the respondents agree that internet banking service is less costly than other banking services.
- Internet banking transaction procedures are simple and straightforward, Majority (62%) of the respondents agree that internet banking transactions are simple.
- The study found that majority (62%) agree that using e-banking is an easy task.
- Majority (51%) of the respondents agreed that e-banking services is being beneficiary for them and is saving their valuable time.
- Most (46%) of the respondents agree that banks are providing timely information about e-banking to the customers.
- Most (48%) of the respondents have proper knowledge about the e-banking transactions.
- Most (38%) of the respondents agreed that Personal data of customers under e-banking is protected.
- Majority (65%) of the respondents agreed that internet banking is more effective than branch banking.
- Majority (65%) of the respondents agreed that websites which offer e-banking services are safe.
- E-banking is convenient because it eliminates the risk of carrying cash, Majority (77%) of the respondents agreed that e-banking is convenient and also it eliminates risk of carrying cash.
- Most (46%) of the respondents agreed that bank authorities solve e-banking problem faced by the customers.

- Majority (68%) of the respondents agree that they like to suggest others to use internet banking.
- The study found that Majority (68%) of the respondents agreed to continue e-banking services, indicates that they are satisfied with e-banking services.
- Respondents overall rating towards e-banking service, Most (32%) of the respondents have rated as 4 out of 5.

Suggestion

- Electronic channel mostly used by both male and female and people living in urban area. It is suggested that the bankers should take measures for creating awareness and educate all kinds of people about electronic channels.
- The young generations are more aware about E-Banking system than older generation. The older generation having less confidence in using E-Banking.
- Due to the complexity and operating methodology. It is suggested that the bankers should take measures for developing confidence about E-Banking operations among older generations.
- The high income groups of customers are having more awareness about E-Banking services than other income group customers. Therefore, the bankers should take necessary steps to create awareness to other income group of customers by way of conducting seminars, exhibition, customer meet, advertisements etc., Among all the E-Banking channels ATM and mobile banking services most familiar among the users.
- The research suggest that the bankers should take much efforts to inculcate knowledge and awareness about other E-Banking channels to the customers. Availability cash in ATM centre is always problematic aspect among the customers. Therefore, it is suggested that the bankers should took care of the availability of cash in ATM centers particularly in remote ATM locations.
- Internet security is the one of the prominent set back of E-Banking operations in many times. The study suggests that the bankers should take initiative and measures for a perfect E-Banking security system.
- The working of e-banking should be updated and also should be made convenient for each and every users. So that customers who are using it and new users can easily make transaction through e-banking services.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, it can be concluded that technology has greatly influenced the bank customers encouraging them to conduct banking in an innovative manner. They have good awareness regarding ATMs and credit card whereas it is low in internet and mobile banking. Variability of adoption of internet banking is high among the different age groups leading. It is further found that internet banking is dependent on education level also where highly educated have high rate of adoption. e-banking service is one of the best tool for both public sectors and private sector banks to reach their valuable customers. In this technological world e-banking is the best example to educate people about banking services which are provided through internet. e-banking services has a great chance to eliminate various barriers which exists in the banking sector. If all the government and banking measures adopted in a right way then e-banking services can rule Indian economy and can also convert Indian banking sector into digital banking sector.

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